

VOCATIONAL SKILL LEARNING DEVELOPMENT FOR INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY CHILDREN

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Abstract-This research was motivated by ability problems in vocational learning for intellectual disability children not optimal yet and ineffective in organizing groups vocational training that held by a few foundation for managing intellectual disability education in Bandung. Based on these circumstances this research aims to: 1) obtain an overview of the objective conditions of vocational learning for intellectual disability children 2) Concepts and theories that are used as referenced in the implementation of this research, comprise: the nature of vocational learning in SLB, the reality in the field that not all of intellectual disability children could get formal education through SLB because of various obstacle such as, distant school distance from their home, limited costs, low parental awareness, also low public awareness. The result of research indicates: the existence of vocational learning not optimal. The conclusion of this research is that vocational skill learning development for intellectual disability children can be said effective in increasing work ability, as knowledge, skill. Recommendation for research results is vocational development for intellectual disability children and can direct them to get a job as provision of their life

Keyword-learning development, Vocational, intellectual disability children, mentally retarded children

1. Introduction

Vocational learning is the process of preparing children to have competencies in the form of life skills to live independently in society. Vocational education for mildly mentally retarded children is largely determined by the extent to which training programs are carried out and the ability of teachers to carry out vocational learning. Therefore it is necessary to formulate and review it to determine the extent of the teacher's ability to implement vocational learning. Based on the results of the study, it will be used as material to reorient the program and improve the quality of services, so that learning for children with intellectual disabilities can be improved and produce children who can support themselves.

Education for mentally retarded children is still faced with various kinds of problems, including the inability of children to master the skills that will be given to children due to limitations so that teachers only provide simple skills and no effort can accommodate mentally retarded children to work. The above problem is if it is not resolved or the way out will result in mentally retarded children becoming people who only rely on other people, even if they are given vocational learning in the form of skills, they can and will acquire skills according to their abilities.

Based on the data, it is not wrong if there is an assumption that the most severe problem faced by mentally retarded children is precisely after graduating from school

because many of them become unemployed and remain a burden on parents.

Education is a sub-system of the supra-system of life that plays a role in the intellectual life of the nation, of course, has a very significant role in the formation of human resources. To produce reliable resources, education must be flexible to various changes and relevant to various developments that occur around it, therefore education in the priority scale of the program is to improve the quality of education that applies to every education and all children.

Based on these objectives, the school as a place for the ongoing education process has the responsibility to provide education as much as possible so that extraordinary children can have competencies in both personal, social and technical competencies that can be applied in daily life. They must be able to fulfill their needs, be able to get along with the community, can have skills so that they can have the skills to live in the community. With the formation of life skills, independence will grow so that extraordinary children will no longer be individuals who have a dependence on others but they can live independently capable of living in life.

- Teacher's ability to develop vocational learning.
- The ability of teachers to manage vocational learning and be able to develop the skills themselves.

- The relevance of developing vocational skills with environmental demands/needs.

The development of vocational learning for mild mentally retarded children must always be relevant to children's needs and environmental needs so that whatever they get from school can be useful for solving various problems in life, and these skills are called life skills.

Based on the background described above, and so that this study is more focused, directed and does not deviate from the main objectives of the study, it is necessary to limit the problems to be studied. From this limitation the following problems are:

- Learning planning made by the teacher.
- Implementation of learning carried out by the teacher.
- Assessment of learning processes and results.
- Constraints faced by teachers in improving vocational learning.
- Strategies to overcome obstacles in improving vocational learning.

The focus of the problem is from the formulation of the problem above, that there are many elements relating to the need to improve the quality of education, so in this study, the authors examine: how to improve vocational learning in SLB in the city of Bandung.

2. Literature Review

A. Understanding of Mentally Retarded

- The general intellectual function is significantly below the average, meaning that the deficiency is convincing so that the concerned person needs special education services, for example, normal children have an average IQ (Intelligence Quotient) 100, while mentally retarded children have the highest IQ 70.
- Deficiencies in adjustment behavior (adaptive behavior), meaning that the person concerned does not / lacks the ability to do jobs that are by his age. He is only able to do work as can be done by children who are younger than him.
- Mental retardation abnormalities are characterized by significant limitations in aspects of intellectual function and adaptive behavior expressed in conceptual, social forms and practices of adaptive skills (Astati, 2004: 4) this definition applies to children whose impairments occur before the age of 18 years.

- From some of these definitions, it can be concluded, that what is meant by mentally retarded children is children who experience irregularities or limitations in development, so that they have difficulty in learning and adjusting to their environment, so they require special education services.

B. Vocational Skill

As stated in PP No. 72 of 1991 Chapter II Article 2 that one of the goals of Special Education is to be able to develop capabilities in the world of work. To answer this fact, Education with Special Needs has long been started in every curriculum change while still including a choice or vocational program which is expected to be an implementation of the life skill vocational program so that mild behaviors can obtain various skills that can be used as a provision for later life and as preparation to enter the world of work, both business and industry.

Following the 2013 curriculum that the chosen program for mild mentally retarded children is:

- Agriculture: Agronomy of Plant Cultivation
- Housekeeping and Tourism: Clothing, Food Beauty
- Arts: Fine Arts and Crafts, Performing Arts

According to the skills that will be trained in exceptional schools, the program has implemented skills packages according to the choice of each school and adapted to the conditions of the school along with the carrying capacity of the school.

From the five skill packages programmed by the Ministry of National Education, it turns out that in schools for mentally retarded children who are already running only household and handicraft. Among them are many who are skilled at making clothes, making various patterns, embroidering, making bags, making cakes, printing and making handicrafts.

Based on the theory of learning above, it is necessary to make various changes in the process, the views of teachers and principals in managing life skills learning, to obtain high-quality graduates who can have various competencies that can be used as a provision in the future life in society.

3. Research Method

In scientific research, there are two approaches, namely quantitative approaches and qualitative approaches. A quantitative approach is a research method that is based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses a quantitative/statistical data analysis research instrument to

test predetermined hypotheses. As stated by Sugiono (2008: 297) as follows "The research method used to produce certain products and test the effectiveness of these products" While the qualitative approach is a research method based on post-positivist philosophy or philosophy of phenomenology that is used to examine the condition of objects that natural (as opposed to experimentation, where the researcher is a key instrument, sampling and data sources are purposive and snowball, collection techniques with triangular (combined), data analysis is inductive/qualitative, and the results of qualitative research emphasize meaning rather than generalization.

In this study, the method used is a qualitative approach or naturalistic inquiry research method. This was chosen to be adjusted to the subject matter of the research that concerns humans individually and in groups. Sugiyono (2013: 6) suggests:

- Research can be divided into academic, professional, and institutional research. In terms of objectives, research can be divided into pure and applied research, while in terms of research methods can be divided into; survey research, ex post facto, experiments, naturalistic, policy research, evaluation research, action research, history, and research and development (R & D).

This study which is considered appropriate for use is the naturalistic inquiry research method, but because this study assesses the three focuses related to humans, evaluation research is also used integratively. There are several studies taken from journals that are relevant "Implementation of Vocational Programs for Children with Impotence" written by Een Ratnanengsih (2017) with the implementation of vocational skills programs that show that the highest obstacle is in the learning aspect (78%). The difficulty in this aspect of learning is how teachers are challenged to be able to design appropriate learning skills for mentally retarded children. The learning process is effective for mentally retarded children, because the condition of mentally retarded children makes it receptive to information, the basic developmental aspects that are hampered cause basic skills in vocational learning to require full mentoring from teachers, Journal "Descriptive study of child employment opportunities post-SMALB mental retardation "Nindya Seva (2017) who said Research Results Related to the problem of employment opportunities for mentally retarded children do tend to be more difficult when compared to children who have other types of disability. Besides, the public's view that is one-eyed, which cannot trust the performance of mentally retarded children is

also one of the obstacles and mental retardation do not get a good job opportunity.

Vocational skills are very important to be given to mild mentally retarded children as a provision after they finish school, skills programs that have been done in schools, vocational education is special education, vocational skills education helps children to explore the talents and interests of children in one job, mentally disabled children can be trained to be semi-skilled labor, mild mentally retarded children can be trained if continuous learning is carried out, they are able to do simple things.

The development of vocational learning must have a goal for the future, the diversity of students in characteristics becomes a difficulty for teachers in developing vocational learning, using an individual approach is expected to help explore the potential that exists in mild mentally retarded children.

4. Conclusion

The importance of educational skills to develop children's abilities in certain skills according to their potential. For mentally retarded children can give appreciation to children as a provision to increase knowledge, the formation of aesthetic experience, the development of creativity and skills in actualizing ideas by the ability of mentally retarded children so that they can be applied in daily life and not always depend on others.

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